

UNSATURATED POLYESTER-SAWDUST COMPOSITES: COMPATIBILIZATION BETWEEN FILLER AND MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to make efficient use of abundant low cost and currently underutilized lignocellulosic materials (sawdust, woodflour), in order to obtain reinforced polymeric composites of high added value.

The work is focused on the role played by the interface-interphase on the mechanical properties of the composite. To effectively know the nature of the interface, the filler was chemically treated and characterized previously to the mixing with the polymeric matrix.

Maleic anhydride was used as sawdust surface modifier. Characterization was carried out by FTIR spectroscopy and water retention methods. An unsaturated polyester resin based on bisphenol A-fumarate was the matrix.

Three point bending tests showed 100% improvement in the flexural modulus of filled samples, although there was no significant difference between treated and untreated filler.

Keywords: wood-by-products; wood polymer interface; vegetable reinforcements; sawdust polyester composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of organic natural fillers (particles and/or fibers) as polymer reinforcement has attracted interest during the last years. The reasons for this interest are mainly the low cost of the material (usually these fillers are low cost by-products or waste materials from other industries) and their abundance and renewability.

In the case of woody fillers, most of the research work has been focused on the reinforcement of thermoplastics and only occasionally on the reinforcement of thermosets.[1] except for phenolic and ureic matrices.

The woody reinforcement of olefinic polymers requires the addition of compatibilizers, in order to enhance the adhesion between filler and matrix with the objective of improving the strength of the composites.[2] Incorporation of the compatibilizer to the composite can be done previously to the kneading process or during it. As an example of the first technique, Maldas et al. studied the effect of silanes and isocyanates on cellulose fiber to be used as filler of polystyrene. However, in this case there was no characterization of the filler after treatment and the mechanical properties of the composites were related to the amount of coupling agent added without confirmation of the efficiency of the treatment.

An example of the second technique is the work of Han et al.,[1] who studied the effect of addition of maleic anhydride (MA) to a wood flour-unsaturated polyester composite.

Incorporation of MA to the material was done during the kneading process, and for this reason it was distributed in an unknown form throughout the whole composite. This problem was mentioned by the authors, since the effect of the coupling agent resulted masked by the changes that occurred in the matrix.

More detailed characterization of wood modified surfaces is reported in studies of chemical modification of vegetable fibers or wood to reduce their water absorption or to change texture properties.[3] However, since in that case, the objective is not the manufacture of composites, the effect of its addition to polymeric resins is not investigated.

The aim of this work is to establish the influence that chemical changes of the resin-woody filler interface exert on the composite mechanical properties. To avoid previous uncertainties, treated and untreated filler surfaces were characterized previously to mixing with the resin. The effectiveness of the chemical modification was determined independently of the properties of the composite and of changes occurred in the matrix due to diffusion of the agent through the resin. For the purpose of this work, an unsaturated polyester resin (UPs) was chosen because of their versatility, low cost and accessibility. Sawdust from local wood was used as reinforcement.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Thermoset Resin

An unsaturated polyester resin based on bisphenol A-fumarate (Perlinac RQ 426) was chosen for the study. It was provided undiluted by Perlinac S.A. (Argentina) in powder form. Characterization of the resin was performed using FTIR spectroscopy, ^{13}C NMR, ^1H NMR and dynamic scanning calorimetry.

FTIR spectra of the resin were obtained using KBr pellets. Peaks appearing at 1509 and 830 cm^{-1} were assigned to *p*-disubstituted benzene (bisphenol A), peaks at 1249 and 1049 cm^{-1} corresponded to aromatic and aliphatic ethers respectively.

^{13}C NMR allowed the identification of four aromatic peaks corresponding to the bisphenol A (region 110 to 160 ppm), aliphatic carbons appearing below 70 ppm and carbon of the carbonyl group at 164 ppm. The peak at 134 ppm was assigned to the carbons of the double bond in the fumarate.

These two analysis indicated that the resin structure contained fumarate and bisphenol A-propyleneglycol ethers.

d-chloroform was the solvent used to dissolve the resin for ^1H NMR. The following peaks were used for the quantitative analysis:[4]

1.62 ppm, methyl groups in bisphenol A,

6.86 ppm, fumarate ($-\text{HC}=\text{CH}-$),

4-4.7 ppm, propyleneglycol (aliphatic H).

The relation among the different components of the resin (bisphenol A / fumarate: 0.91-1.2; bisphenol A / propyleneglycol: 0.54), as well as the double bond content (2.18×10^{-3} mole C=C / g resin).

The glass transition temperature of the resin was of 53 °C, measured by DSC (DuPont 990) at 10 °C/min.

Benzoyl peroxide (Lucidol 75%, Akzo Chemical S.A.) was used as initiator (1.5 % by weight). The water present was removed by mixing the commercial initiator with styrene. The peroxide passed to the organic phase, which was separated by centrifugation. The styrene used as solvent of the peroxide was taken into account in the calculations of the crosslinker. Styrene (Poliresinas San Luis S.A., Argentina) was used as crosslinking agent (35% by weight).

2.1.2. Woody Fillers

Sawdust from *Eucalyptus Saligna* (density approx. 0.83 kg/dm^3 ; Entre Ríos, Argentina) was the filler. Figure 1 shows the screen analysis of the filler. A Tyler series of 70-100-120-150-200-250-300 mesh was used in the analysis. Particles retained in mesh 40 were discarded. The major fraction of the particles (about 76%) was between 0.2 and 0.37 mm, particles of less than 0.1 mm

were less than 7 % of the mixture. Sawdust was dried in an oven at 60°C until constant weight was obtained.

Particles were treated by addition of maleic anhydride. Sawdust was immersed in a solution of maleic anhydride in acetone (8% by weight w.r.t sawdust). In some samples an 8% of sulfuric acid was also added. In both cases, samples were left in contact with the anhydride during one day at room temperature. Then, solids were separated and half of each type of the samples were washed four times in acetone and oven-dried until constant weight was verified.

Figure 1. Sawdust size distribution used in the preparation of the composites.

Characterization of the treated and untreated sawdust was done using water retention value measurements [5] and FTIR spectroscopy. In both cases the finest fraction of the distribution was used, since it was the one with the largest surface to volume ratio, it was more accessible to chemical treatment and characterization.

2.2. Sample Preparation

Resin specimens were obtained using glass molds. Mixing was manually carried out, dissolving first the UPs powder in styrene and adding the peroxide-styrene solution.

Filled samples were prepared by compression molding in metallic molds. As in resin specimens, a silicone release agent was used to provide good demolding. An intensive mixer (Brabender type) was used to blend the resin with sawdust (40% by weight).

Both, filled and unfilled systems, were cured 2 hours at 50 °C, then 24 hours at 80 °C and finally 2 hours at 150 °C (post-curing stage).

Specimens to be tested in three point bending [6] were cut from the molded plates.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Crosslinking reaction

The heat of reaction of the system (UPs, benzoyl peroxide, styrene) was measured by DSC (from 23 to 180 °C at 10 °C/min) and found equal to 295 J / g. J. C. Lucas found that the heat of reaction per double bond was constant (for an unsaturated polyester resin and different concentrations of styrene crosslinker) and equal to 65626 joule / mole of double bonds.[7] Using

this value and the double bond concentration, it was possible to calculate the conversion, which was of 93.7 %.

3.2. Sawdust modification

To quantify the level of treatment of the filler, the fraction of sawdust with average diameter between 48-57 μ was used. Determination of the amount of maleic anhydride chemically reacted to the wood surface was done using different techniques: titration, water retention value and FTIR spectroscopy.

After treatment sawdust was separated by centrifugation. This solution was titrated with NaOH aq. and the amount of reacted maleic anhydride was calculated by difference with the values obtained for a blank solution. The determination required the use of a pH-meter since the liquid is slightly colored. When the treatment included H₂SO₄, 3.120 \pm 0.15 mg of reacted maleic anhydride / g of sawdust was measured. Without addition of acid the measured value was 0.156 \pm 0.24 mg of reacted maleic anhydride / g of sawdust. The dispersion was too high in the last case to assure that the anhydride had effectively reacted with the woody particles. Due to this uncertainty, other type of measurements was performed.

Water retention technique measures the water that can not be extracted by mechanical means. It reveals changes in the hygroscopicity of the sample.[5] Sawdust was immersed in distilled water and then centrifuged to separate them. Difference between the weight of the wet and dried samples related to the weight of the dried samples (expressed as a percentage) is called the water retention value of the sample. Table 1 shows the measured values. They are in the same order of magnitude than others reported in the literature for vegetable fibers with and without treatments.[8]

Table 1. Water Retention Values (WRV)

		After washing in acetone
Untreated sawdust (A) ^a	6.28	
Sawdust + MA	5.05 (B)	5.56 (C)
Sawdust + MA+ H ₂ SO ₄	4.96 (D)	5.11 (E)

^a Untreated sawdust was subject to immersion in acetone in the same conditions as the other samples to reduce possible differences due to extractables.

The reported values showed that both treatments produce changes in the hygroscopicity of the samples, but these were more important in the case of addition of sulfuric acid. After washing the samples in acetone the WRV decreases, indicating that some of the maleic anhydride was weakly attached to the surface and could be removed. However, a difference between the untreated sawdust and the washed treated samples remained, thus, some of the anhydride must have been chemically attached onto the woody particles or at least strongly physically adsorbed.

Diffuse reflectance (DRIFT) spectra of the above samples were also obtained. The equipment utilized was a Bruker IFS 25 and the DRIFT cell was a Barnes Analytical / Spectra Tech. Each sample diluted in KBr powder was run using 500 scans and 2 cm⁻¹ resolution. Figure 2 shows the DRIFT spectra of samples A, B and C mentioned in Table 1. Spectra of sawdust treated with MA in the presence of sulfuric acid (samples D and E) showed that important changes occurred in the wood due to the oxidizing character of the strong acid used, and are not included.

Spectra of the untreated sawdust (A) shows a good signal to noise ratio. Peak assignment was done using Reference 9, which includes the vibrations corresponding to most of the main peaks as well as the possible source (lignin, cellulose or hemicellulose).

Comparison of spectra A and B shows some differences in the region of 600-2000 cm⁻¹. At 1704 cm⁻¹, in the region of C=O stretch, a new peak appears for the treated sawdust, which is attributed to the C=O stretch in maleates.

At 1670 cm⁻¹ spectrum A shows a weak peak assigned to stretch of carbonyl in lignin. Spectrum B shows also a wider medium intensity peak at 1635 cm⁻¹, which is assigned to the C=C of the maleate.

Figure 2. DRIFT spectra of sawdust. A- Spectrum of the untreated filler (washed in acetone), B- Spectrum of the MA treated filler, C- Spectrum of the MA treated filler (washed in acetone).

At 820 and 861 cm^{-1} , the spectrum of the treated sawdust (B) shows two peaks that are absent in the untreated sawdust spectrum. They are assigned to C=C wag. All the new peaks that appear after treatment correlate well with those appearing in the spectra of maleates.[10] Spectrum C shows the same differences discussed for sample B. However, in this case all new peaks appear with lower intensities, indicating that some of the MA can be washed out with acetone.

DRIFT spectroscopy and WRV measurements allowed to confirm that MA treatment was at least partially effective, even under the mild reaction conditions used. In the future a non-oxidant acid and higher reaction temperatures will be used to favor the esterification reaction.

3. 3 Flexural results

Flexural strength and flexural modulus were determined from the mechanical test performed. The results are presented in Table 2:

Table 2. Flexural properties.

	E_b [GPa]	σ_b [MPa]
UPs	3.62	107 ± 17
Untreated filler + UPs	7.9 ± 0.6	62 ± 3
Treated filler + UPs	6.2 ± 0.8	54 ± 8

The inclusion of sawdust produced a decrease in the flexural strength, about 50%, but there is an 100% improvement in the flexural modulus of the filled samples. Unfortunately the chemical treatment of the filler has not produced a significant change in the properties with respect to the samples with untreated filler.

M2-drift-18/2/93

Date: 18/02/93 Time: 12:08:29

High: 4000.00 Low: 600.00 NDP: 3400 Data Int.: 1.000 Der: 0

Bascor: yes Norm: yes Sys: FT-IR

Logabs: no Command: AddC Mode: AU

4. CONCLUSIONS

Sawdust surface treatment was performed using maleic anhydride to enhance the compatibility with the unsaturated polyester matrix.

FTIR and WRV revealed that there was effective modification of the filler under the mild conditions used. Even after washing with solvent, sawdust retained part of the MA, indicating that chemical or strongly physical attachments were created during treatment.

Preliminary mechanical tests showed an increase in flexural modulus and a decrease in flexural strength of the filled UPs compared to the unfilled matrix. There were no significant differences between composites prepared with treated or untreated sawdust.

A non-oxidant acid and higher reaction temperatures will be used in the future, to favor the esterification reaction.

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